

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF SHEARING THICKENING FLUID (STF) DAMPERS

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1 Introduction

It is well known that the structural response could be reduced appropriately by installing damper devices. However, the damper deployed on buildings or bridges are generally designed only for the specific structural system under certain loading conditions. As a result, several researchers have developed the adjustable passive damper in recent years [1][2]. Electrorheological dampers (ER dampers) and magnetorheological (MR dampers) dampers are well known the adjustable damper systems, but the durability and the stability of the external power supply needed for MR and ER dampers are doubtful questions for the long-term application during structure service life. Consequently, a new material, shear thickening fluids (STF), which changes its properties according to different loading rate without external power needed are considered to be a good filled material for innovative damper devices [3]. Lee et al. applied STF to develop the liquid body armor which is bullet proof with flexibility [4]. Fisher et al. focused on the feasibility of integrating STFs into a composite sandwich structure which can lead simultaneously to changes in stiffness and damping under dynamic flexural loading as the strain and/or frequency are varied [5]. This paper studies the feasibility of applying STF materials on a conventional viscous damper device by using a simplified piston device and changing the concentration of STF filled to develop an innovative passive damper which behaves like the MR damper. In this study, STF samples which were composed of nanosize fumed silica particles suspended in a solvent PEG (polypropylene glycol) were fabricated in the laboratory. The shear properties of STF samples under the steady state and the oscillatory state were tested separately by using a rheometer. Furthermore, a prototype STF damper

was developed and tested with preliminary performance experiments, followed by analytical models studied. Besides, hysteretic loops of the STF damper developed under various loading conditions were observed. The result shows the feasibility of the STF damper proposed in this paper and indicates that it might have a good potential in practical engineering applications.

2 Preliminary Performance Experiments

2.1 STFs Materials

This paper used the STF material which contains hydrophilic fumed silica (Aerosil R972) with a primary spherical particle size of 14 nm and a specific surface area approximately 200 m²/g for performance experiments. The carrier fluid is polypropylene glycol (H[OCH(CH₃)CH₂]_nOH) with an average molar mass 1000 g/mol. In each experimental study case, the carrier fluid was mixed with fumed silica particles by using a blender (Fig. 1.) to mechanically stir the two components into uniform distribution.

Fig.1. Blender.

In order to get well dispersion STF, the suspensions after the stirring procedure were conducted to pass three-roll mill (Fig. 2.) six times. A three-roll mill is a mechanical tool that utilizes the shear force created by three horizontally positioned rolls rotating at opposite directions and different speeds relative to each other to mix, refine, disperse, or homogenize viscous materials fed into it. Finally, the fully mixed

STFs were placed in a vacuum chamber to eliminate bubbles inside the STF. Regarding to the concentrations of the STF conducted in this study are 7.5%, 10%, and 12.5 %w/w (Fig. 3.).

Fig.2. Three-roll mill.

Fig.3. STF materials.

2.2 Rheological Tests and Results

As for rheological tests, rheological measurements were performed on a stress-controlled Rheometrics Scientific AR2000ex rheometer (Fig. 4a.).

Fig.4. (a) rheometer (b) cone and plate

Varied dynamic frequency tests were conducted by using a 40 mm diameter cone-plate tool (Fig. 4b.) with a cone angle of 4 degree and a gap of 0.4 mm between the plate and the twitter. Figure 5 shows the experimental result of relationship between the viscosity and the shear rate of the carrier fluid

applied under steady state. It shows that the polypropylene glycol matrix is a Newtonian fluid whose viscosity keeps at constant value under different shear rate.

Fig.5. Viscosity as a function of shear rate for PPG.

Figure 6 shows the experimental result of the relationship between the dynamic viscosity and the shear rate of STF material applied under 10% concentrations. The results show that STF fluids have high nonlinear behavior, and perform from low to high amplitude strains at different shear angular frequencies of 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 rad s⁻¹, respectively. The STF exhibits strain thickening at high strain amplitudes, with its complex viscosity showing an abrupt jump to higher levels at particular strains for different shear frequencies. The data in Figure 6 indicates that the transition to a strain-thickening behavior occurs at smaller strains as the frequency of the deformation is increased.

Fig.6. Dynamic strain sweeps at different angular frequencies for 10% (w/w).

According to the experimental data, figure 7 gives the response of the 10% (w/w) STF for a critical shear strain γ_c and the strain at the end of the transition, γ_m , as a function of ω . This figure could be used to predict whether the STF was in the low viscosity state, in the transition state or in the shear-thickened state.

Fig.7. γ_c and γ_m as a function of angular frequency.

3 STF Damper Developed

The mechanism of STF damper developed is similar to a conventional single-tube damper which consists of a piston, one flow tunnel and a cylinder (Fig. 8.). It consists 4 parts elements including cylinder, piston head, oil seal and fluid.

Fig.8. Drawing of STF damper developed.

The photo of experimental layout of dynamic performance tests is shown in Figure 9. The STF damper was tested under harmonic excitations with different frequencies at fixed stroke. In this paper, the range of test frequencies is from 0.01Hz to 3 Hz according with the constant stroke of 1mm to 15mm (Table 1.).

Fig.9. Layout of STF damper performance test.

The experimental results in terms of damping force versus displacement at different frequencies are shown in figure 10. For each test, 6 cycles were repeated, and average values were taken to obtain

the stabilized hysteresis loops. As can be seen from figure 10, the shape of the displacement damping force loop is strongly dependent on the loading frequency. For example, the peak damping force shows an increasing trend with frequency. In the low frequency range, such as 1 Hz, the STF presents a Newtonian fluid character. The area of the hysteretic loop per cycle denotes the energy dissipation capability. As the excitation frequency increases, the slope of the low velocity hysteresis loop increases. The damper works in the low viscosity state, in the transition state and in the shear thickened state when the excitation frequency is at 3 and 5 Hz, respectively. The hysteresis loop changes significantly as the excitation frequency passes 1 Hz.

Frequency (Hz)	Amplitude (mm)			
	1	5	10	15
0.1	0.63	3.14	6.28	9.42
0.3	1.88	9.42	18.85	28.27
0.5	3.14	15.71	31.42	47.12
1	6.28	31.42	62.83	94.25
3	18.85	94.25	188.50	282.74
5	31.42	157.08	314.16	471.24
10	62.83	314.16	628.32	942.48

Table1. Harmonic excitations test under different frequencies at fixed stroke.

Fig.10. (a) 1mm stroke (b) 5mm stroke (c) 10mm stroke (d) 15mm stroke. Hysteretic loop of the 10% (w/w) STF damper.

Fig.11. Force-Velocity chart of 10%(w/w)STF damper.

Furthermore, the results of damping force versus velocity is shown in figure 11, it presents that the STF-filled damper device has varied kind of damping coefficient with different loading frequencies. By applying such behavior characteristic, the developed device might be used for structural semi-passive control applications under different loading criteria. As a result, the preliminary experimental has put it into proven that the feasibility of STF-filled damper device.

4 Summary and Discussion

This study has indicated that the STF material, which is composed of nanosize fumed silica particles suspended in a solvent, can be used as damping elements to fill in the viscous damper device. Preliminary experimental tests result have shown that the STF damper developed can lead simultaneously to changes in damping under dynamic loading with varied frequencies or stroke. The result also points that the velocity of dynamic loading has a significant influence on the fluid viscous properties, which has a large influence on the energy absorption response during the working of the damper. And it can be said that STF damper could be considered as an innovative passive damper device for structural applications in the future.

Moreover, there are few topics will be further studied in the future. First, the settlement of fumed silica in STF. If the Brownian movement of nanoparticles is larger than itself weight, the probability of settlement is quite rare. In order to study this phenomenon, the STF fluid will be placed for six months and the rheological properties will be compared with new-made STF.

Second, the study of engineering application. In order to develop a design method of STF damper for engineering application, it is important to build the database of STF fluid as figure 7 shows and use the CFD 全文? program, ANSYS as for example, is used to simulate the dynamics behavior STF-filled traditional viscous damper, to replace the full-scale behavior test. It can be predicted the STF-filled traditional viscous damper performance by CFD program.

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